

LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIORS OF MULTI AXIAL WARP KNITTED FABRIC COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

Low-cycle fatigue properties and stress relaxation behavior in warp knitted fabric composite were investigated. The strength design with the knee point was significant for fatigue properties. And the decrease of elasticity obtained by time-temperature superposition principle in the specimen with damage was bigger than the specimen with no damage.

Keywords: Low-cycle fatigue behaviors, Multi axial warp knitted fabric, Crack progress, Initial fracture, Hybrid composite

INTRODUCTION

The initial fracture of composite materials is the micro-fractures. It is known that the final fracture of materials is caused by the accumulation of the micro-fractures. Fig.1 shows schematic drawing of the micro-fractures. The micro-fractures of fiber-reinforced composite materials are fiber rupture [1], resin crack, transverse crack, fracture between fiber and resin, and delamination between layers etc.

There is a knee point in the stress-strain curve of composite materials as shown in Fig.2. Knee point is defined as a dropping off point from the initial elastic region. Knee point appears in consequence of the initial micro-fractures [2,3]. The initial fracture normally occurs at lower stress than the final fracture stress. After knee point, micro-fractures are progressed and accumulated until final fracture.

Generally, the fatigue test is performed to decide fatigue characteristic of materials. A cyclic stress is loaded to a specimen in this method and a number of cycles until final fracture are investigated. As a result of fatigue test, relationship between applied stress and number of cycles to fracture is investigated and fatigue limit can be obtained from S-N curve. Today, the strength design of fatigue is determined by applying this fatigue limit.

However, as above mentioned, this method has been performed for the macroscopic evaluation and micro damage isn't considered. Fracture of composite materials is caused by the accumulation of various micro fractures. The fracture progresses even if low stress is loaded in the materials with micro damage. Therefore it is difficult to use general fatigue evaluation for composite materials. That is to say, particular strength

design of fatigue that micro damage is considered should be required for composite materials. In this study, the knee point was focused on as the index of the fatigue.

The reinforcement used in this study was multi-axial warp knitted fabric as shown in Fig.3. Multi-axial warp knitted fabric is a kind of textile in which unidirectional fiber bundles are aligned and knitted at some angle by warp knitting technology [4]. Higher mechanical performance resulted from no climp of fiber bundle is achieved compared with the general textile composites [5-7]. This fabric can be treated as one layer, so that stacking process can be decreased, and fabrication cost of composite structures can be reduced [8]. Moreover, hybrid composites can be fabricated by the introduction of two or more reinforcements. For these reasons, it is used in various field such as structure of ship and windmill blade etc [9,10].

The purpose of this study is to investigate the verification of the index with the knee point for fatigue properties and stress relaxation behavior in the material with low-cycle fatigue. In the investigation of the index with the knee point, the crack occurrence and progress were clarified from low-cycle bending fatigue test and the cross-sectional observation. At first, static bending test was performed to calculate knee point from the stress-deflection curves. Secondary low-cycle bending fatigue test was performed to provide above and below the stress at knee point to investigate the crack occurrence and progress. Finally cross-section of the specimen in arbitrary number of cycle was observed. As a consequence, crack occurrence, fracture morphology and crack propagation were clarified. In the investigation of the stress relaxation behavior, three-point bending stress relaxation test was performed under the water by using the specimen with low-cycle fatigue and the specimen with no damage. Finally, relationships between elastic modulus and time were investigated under the atmosphere of low, middle and high temperature. And relationships between elastic modulus and time under high temperature were shifted towards time axis by applying time-temperature superposition principle. As a result, a master curve can be drawn, and long life estimation such as 50 years of the material could be discussed by the master curve.

Fig.1 Schematic drawing of micro-fractures

Fig.2 Calculation method of knee point

Fig.3 Schematic drawing of the multi-axial warp knitted fabric

Material

Fig.4 shows multi-axial warp knitted fabric in this study. It had a structure that unidirectional reinforcing fiber bundles are aligned in 0 and 90 directions and linked with knitted yarn. Knitted yarn was polyester fiber. Two kinds of fiber bundles, glass fiber (Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd. JAPAN) and carbon fiber (HTA-12K; Toho Tenax Co., Ltd. JAPAN) were used in 0/90 multi-axial warp knitted fabric. Unsaturated polyester resin (RIGORAC 150HRBQNTNW; SHOWA HIGHPOLYMER CO., LTD. JAPAN) was used as matrix resin. Multi-axial warp knitted fabric composite with $[0/90]_s$ laminate was molded by hand lay-up method. The thickness was 1.6mm. The fiber volume fraction, V_f of specimens was 43%.

Fig.5 shows schematic drawings of laminates. In the case of Glass/Glass (G/G), glass fiber bundle was used both for 0 and 90 layers. In inter-layer hybrid composite (C/G), 0 layer was carbon fiber and 90 layer was glass fiber respectively.

Fig.4 0/90 multi-axial warp knitted fabric

Fig.5 Schematic drawings of specimens of fiber bundle's distribution

Low-cycle Fatigue Test

Specimen dimension was 70×20 mm. Low-cycle bending fatigue test was performed as span length of 52mm. Testing was conducted by using Instron universal testing machine (Type55R4206) with cross head speed of 5mm/min. First of all, static bending test was performed to obtain stress at knee point. Then low-cycle bending fatigue test was performed by providing cyclic load. Fig.6 shows applied load cycle curves. Total number of cycle was 103. Cross-sectional observation at every 10 cycles was performed. To carry out the observation the edge of specimen was polished before testing. A reflection type optical microscope was used for cross-sectional observation.

Fig.6 Applied load cycle curves

Results and Discussion

Fig.7 shows bending stress-deflection curves of each specimen. The fracture deflection and strength of G/G were higher than C/G. In this study, stress at knee point was calculated from magnified stress-deflection curves. Table1 shows the summary of bending properties of each specimen. Bending modulus of G/G was 27.9GPa, and C/G was 72.9GPa. Stress at knee point of G/G and C/G was 275MPa and 385MPa respectively. Low-cycle bending fatigue test was performed below and above the stress at knee point. In the case of low-cycle bending fatigue test above the stress at knee point, the applied stress was 280MPa in G/G and 390MPa in C/G. In the case of low-cycle bending fatigue test below the stress at knee point, the crack initiation was not observed.

Fig.8 and Fig.9 shows the photographs and schematic drawings of the cross-section of G/G and C/G at each cycle above the stress at knee point. The initial fracture of each

specimen occurred in the fiber bundle of 90 direction layer. It was the debonding between filament and resin. As cyclic load increased, many debonding occurred, and these debonding were linked and finally became a transverse crack. On the other hand, the crack was not observed in the fiber bundle of 0 direction layer.

Fig.10 shows photographs of cross-sectional observation after 103rd cycle. Regardless of type of specimen, the crack propagation behavior was same. The transverse crack caused by debonding between filament and resin was progressed in the fiber bundle of 90 direction layer. The direction of crack propagation was from 0 direction layer to neutral axis. The multiple transverse cracks were observed in one fiber bundle. The number of cracks per fiber bundle of G/G and C/G were same.

The crack length of each cycle was measured to evaluate crack progress quantitatively. In both G/G and C/G, numbers of crack and fracture morphology after 103 cycles were same as mentioned above. Then, the crack length per bundle was calculated from photograph of cross-sectional observation. Fig.11 shows the crack length in each cycle. The final crack lengths of G/G and C/G were same. In G/G, crack progressed drastically between first and second cycles. After second cycles, crack progressed gradually and after 23 cycles crack length became constant. On the other hand, crack of C/G progressed gradually between third and 63th. It was thought that the difference of crack progress was attributed to the type of fiber bundle in 0 direction layer.

In order to discuss the difference of crack propagation, bending stress of each layer under the stress at knee point was calculated with composite beam theory. The normal stress in 0 direction layer of G/G and C/G were 87.3MPa and 127.3MPa. The normal stress in 90 direction layer of G/G and C/G were 27.8MPa and 13.1MPa. Those are the initial fracture stress in 90 direction layer. The reinforcement of 90 direction both of G/G and C/G was the glass fiber. Therefore the initial fracture stress should be same value. But in the theoretic calculation, initial fracture stress in 90 direction layer of G/G was higher value than that of C/G.

It was considered that the difference was affected by the hybrid constitution such as glass fiber and carbon fiber. Therefore, the residual stress was noticed as one of the investigation of the effect. The stress in the 90 direction was different by residual stress at the post cure. Then the residual stress was calculated by laminate theory.

According to the results, the residual stress of G/G in 90 direction layer was almost 0MPa, and that of C/G in 90 direction layer was 17.0MPa. When the initial fracture stress obtained from composite beam theory and residual stress were added, total stress of G/G and C/G were same.

Fig.12 shows the schematic drawing of stress distribution in each layer. In this study, it was assumed that the residual stress within 90 direction layer was not uniform. It was considered that stress in the 90 direction layer was high at adjacent 0 direction layer. From the experiments, initial fracture occurred at the point within 90 direction layer near 0 direction layer side. Moreover, it is thought that in the fiber bundle of 90 direction layer, the residual stress tends to decrease with increase in distance from the layer of 0 direction since the influence of the constraint by 0 direction layer tends to be small. Therefore, in the crack propagation of C/G, the crack progressed gradually after the initiation because of lower stress in the center area within 90 direction layer. On the

other hand, in the G/G, the difference in stress at 90 direction layer was not existed. Therefore, in the crack propagation of G/G, the crack progressed drastically after the initiation.

Fig.7 Stress-Deflection curves

Table1 Summary of bending properties

	Modulus(GPa)	Strength(MPa)	Stress at knee point(MPa)
G/G	27.9	821.9	275
C/G	72.9	724.3	385

Fig.8 Photographs and schematic drawings of the cross-section of G/G

Fig.9 Photographs and schematic drawings of the cross-section of C/G

(a) G/G

(b) C/G

Fig.10 Fracture aspect of fiber bundle after 103 cycle

Fig.11 Degree of crack progress

Fig.12 stress distribution of C/G composite

Stress Relaxation Test

Stress relaxation test was performed to clarify the durability. Therefore two types of specimen were used. One was “Blank”, which was the specimen with no low-cycle fatigue, and the other was “low-cycle specimen”, which was the specimen with low-cycle fatigue. Specimen dimension was 120×20 mm. Maximum and minimum applied stress is 300% and 10% higher value than stress at knee point. Number of cycle is 50 cycles. Three-point bending stress relaxation test was performed under the water. The temperature conditions were 30, 40, 50 °C. Span length was 100mm. The applied deflection was 4.5mm as elasticity region.

Results and Discussion

As a result of stress relaxation test, elasticity was calculated using reaction force. Fig.13 shows the relationships between the elasticity and the logarithm of the testing time in blank and low-cycle specimen. The value of elasticity in the low-cycle specimen was lower than that of blank. The difference of the elasticity was due to a lot of micro-fracture such as delamination and transverse crack. Next, when the curve in 30°C was considered as a standard, two curves in 40°C and 50°C were shifted towards time axis by applying time-temperature superposition principle.

Fig.13 Elasticity reduction curves

Fig.14 show master curves in each specimen. Compared the result of blank with the result of low-cycle specimen, the tendency of two master curves was different. Fig.15 shows the relationship between ratios of E/E_0 and logarithm of the testing time. Here E_0 means initial elasticity. In the case of low-cycle specimen, elasticity reduction was bigger than that of blank. Therefore it was considered that the fracture progressed even if the applied deflection was under elastic region.

Fig.14 Master curves

In addition, Fig.16 shows shift factor in each specimen. The activation energy was obtained from tendency of shift factor. The activation energy means the energy needed to deform the material. The activation energy of low-cycle specimen was lower than

that of blank. For this reason, micro-fracture existed in the specimen with low-cycle fatigue. And the elasticity of low-cycle specimen was lower than that of blank. Consequently, it was easy to be deformed due to low bending stiffness in the low-cycle specimen. As a result, the activation energy was lower than that of blank.

Fig.15 relationship between ratios of E/E_0 and $\log(t)$

Fig.16 Shift factor

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the verification of the index with the knee point for fatigue properties. Two kinds of multi-axial warp knitted fabric, G/G and C/G, were used and fatigue characteristics of them were investigated.

In the case of below the stress at knee point, the crack initiation was not observed. In above the stress at knee point, the initial fracture was the debonding between filament and resin in the fiber bundle of 90 direction regardless of the types of specimens. As cyclic load increased, these debonding were linked and became transverse crack.

It was found that the crack progresses of G/G and C/G were different. In order to discuss the difference of crack propagation, bending stress of each layer under the stress at knee point was calculated with composite beam theory. The normal stress in 90

direction layer of G/G was higher than C/G. Then the residual stress was calculated by lamination theory. Residual stress of C/G was higher than that of G/G. When the initial fracture stress obtained from composite beam theory and residual stress were added, total stress of G/G and C/G were same. The difference of the crack propagation was caused by the distribution of the residual stress in 90 direction layer. Consequently the strength design with the knee point is significant for the fatigue properties.

And stress relaxation behavior was investigated by using two types of specimens, blank and low-cycle specimen. As a result, elasticity reduction of low-cycle specimen in the master curve was bigger than that of blank. This difference was attributed to the micro-fracture such as debonding between fiber and resin and transverse crack existed in the specimen. Therefore it was important to prevent the occurrence of micro-fracture.

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